

NOTES

Mixed Ligand Complexes of Indium(III) with Indole Mannich Base and Salicylaldehyde

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A number of indium(III) complexes have been prepared in neutral and alkaline media by Sallomi and Al-Dahar^{1,2}. Some indole derivatives have been reported to exhibit auxin activity. The present paper reports the synthesis and spectral characteristics of mixed In^{III} chelates with 3-(α -naphthyl)aminomethylindole (L) and salicylaldehyde (HL').

Experimental

3-(α -Naphthyl)aminomethylindole and salicylaldehyde were prepared according to literature procedure³.

A mixture of ethanolic solution of the metal salt, InX₃ (where X=Cl, Br and NO₂) and the ligand solutions in the metal-M : L-HL' molar ratio 1 : 1 : 1, was stirred and refluxed for 40-45 min on a water-bath at about 70°. The resulting crystalline solids were washed with ethanol, acetone and finally with dry ether and dried under reduced pressure over P₂O₅.

Comparison of the ir spectra of the ligand (L) and the complexes shows that ν_{NH} band observed at 3 380 cm⁻¹ in 3-(α -naphthyl)aminomethylindole, shifted to 3 345-3 340 cm⁻¹ region in the spectra of the complexes. Similarly, a strong band due to $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ found at $\sim$ 1 340 cm⁻¹ in the ligand, appears at 1 300-1 310 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the complexes. This suggests that both the nitrogen atoms, present in the ligand (L), are involved in coordination with the metal ion.

ν_s and ν_{as} vibrations of OH in N-OH group, observed at 3 310 and 3 205 cm⁻¹ in salicylaldehyde⁴, are seen as such in the spectra of the complexes, showing non-involvement of this group in complexation. But $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ band found at 1 650 cm⁻¹ in the ligand, shifted to lower frequency band (1 630-1 605 cm⁻¹) in the spectra of the complexes, showing its involvement in coordination through nitrogen atom. A broad band of the ligand at 3 560 cm⁻¹ (phenolic OH) is absent in the spectra of the complexes, showing its deprotonation and involvement of its oxygen atom in the bond formation with the metal ion.

New bands at $\sim$ 490 and 410 cm⁻¹ are assigned as $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ vibrations respectively. The low frequency band appearing at 170-240 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the halo complexes, is assigned as $\nu_{\text{M-X}}$ (where X=Cl, Br). The absence of the ν_s band ($\sim$ 1 350 cm⁻¹) indicating ionic nature of nitrate and the presence of strong bands at 1 510 and 1 285 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the nitrate complex, suggest the coordination nature of nitrate. Absence of any band at 1 025, 800 and 725 cm⁻¹ indicates its monodentate nature.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				
	C	H	N	In	Halogen
[In(C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₂)(C ₇ H ₆ NO ₂)Cl ₂]	52.08 (52.55)	3.68 (3.70)	7.11 (7.07)	19.20 (19.88)	11.86 (11.94)
[In(C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₂)(C ₇ H ₆ NO ₂)Br ₂]	45.85 (45.69)	3.20 (3.22)	6.20 (6.15)	16.88 (16.81)	23.30 (23.43)
[In(C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₂)(C ₇ H ₆ NO ₂)(NO ₂) ₂]	47.96 (48.23)	3.37 (3.40)	10.90 (10.82)	17.64 (17.75)	—

Results and Discussion

Analytical data (Table I) correspond to the composition [In(C₁₀H₁₆N₂)(C₇H₆NO₂)X₂] for the isolated complexes. They are insoluble in common organic solvents but soluble in DMSO, DMF and dioxan. They show non-electrolytic behaviour as evidenced by low conductance data (8-10 Ω^{-1} cm² mol⁻¹ in DMSO).

References

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